

A 170mV-to-1.8V Input Voltage Range DC-DC Boost Converter Using a 100nH Air-coil with Sub- μ A Quiescent Current

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Abstract— This paper introduces a sub- μ A DC-DC boost converter designed to function with input voltages between 170mV and 1.8V. The wide input voltage operating range of the proposed converter allows to extract most of the charge out of a supercapacitor, intermittently charged by a wireless powering system. It is the first converter working with this large (10x) input voltage range, while utilizing a mm-sized MRI-compatible 100nH air-coil, making it well-suited for miniature active medical implants. By using the proposed peak current circuit, the converter can achieve \sim ns on-time control with only 1μ A of quiescent current. Despite the low-power consumption and large input voltage operating range, the peak current was regulated within 6.75% from its optimal value of 50mA. Finally, the proposed DC-DC converter achieves a peak efficiency of 95.82% even if using a miniature air-coil inductor.

Keywords— DC-DC boost converter, \sim nH air-coil, discontinuous conduction mode (DCM), ultra-low power, peak current control technique

I. INTRODUCTION

Efficient powering of miniature active medical implants remains a challenge. Conventional powering solutions rely on batteries. However, batteries are bulky, require careful safety considerations and need replacement, rendering them unsuitable for powering active medical implants. While wireless powering and energy harvesting solutions have been investigated, they still necessitate an intermediate energy storage between the circuits extracting power and the biosensors, particularly when dealing with intermittent power levels. Because of their small size and biocompatibility, supercapacitors are becoming an interesting choice. Compared to batteries, they have much lower energy density but are characterized by a linear discharge curve. To extract most of the energy stored in the supercap, a highly efficient DC-DC boost converter is needed to operate reliably also with low input voltages. Fig 1 shows the system architecture of the wirelessly powered active implant. The DC-DC boost converter proposed in this paper is responsible for extracting energy from the supercap and boosting it to a suitable voltage level to power the implantable electronic system.

In miniature implants, large coils are unacceptable. Furthermore, to extend the application domain of the wirelessly powered active implants system represented in Fig. 1, mm-sized, MRI-compatible air-coils (\sim nH) are needed. However, such coils require extremely fast switch controls (with \sim ns response times) to operate around the optimal peak current despite the large variations of the converter’s input voltage. This means that,

to keep the inductor peak current equal to I_{PEAK} , the on-time (T_{ON}) of the switch M_N has to be inversely proportional to the input voltage V_{IN} : $T_{ON} = (L * I_{PEAK}) / V_{IN}$.

Conventional voltage-mode controls suffer from efficiency losses to keep the control loop stable [1], while current-mode controls can be made unconditionally stable and allow the converter to operate at its optimal peak current. However, current-mode controls normally require high-speed control circuits, which typically rely on power-hungry inductor current measurements. [4,5] achieve <10 ns response time but still consume $>350\mu$ W, which is orders of magnitude more than the μ W quiescent current target of this work.

Fig. 1 System architecture of the wirelessly powered active implants

Feedforward current sensor topologies [2] (Fig. 2a) don’t measure the inductor current directly but control the on-time of M_N (T_{ON}) by measuring the input voltage (in case of a boost topology) to avoid the inherent power consumption, and hence efficiency losses, associated with current sensing. Despite its input voltage V_{IN} is almost DC, the buffer has to discharge the capacitor C_{ON} after each conversion cycle. This implies that the buffer’s settling time needs to be fast enough to avoid limiting the operating frequency of the converter.

In this work, we propose a new architecture for controlling the peak current (Fig. 2b) that consumes only 280nA quiescent current, while achieving $\pm 6.75\%$ peak current accuracy over a large input voltage range of 170mV to 1.8V. Contrary to other implementations, this architecture only requires low-speed active circuits by using a current sampler and switch to synchronize the current I_{ON} to the converter switching frequency. A transconductor (TC) converts the (scaled) input voltage V_{INS} into a current I_{TC} . Given that the ratio between V_{IN} and V_{INS} is 3, the minimum TC's input voltage will be only 56mV, making the current control accuracy strongly affected by offset and low-frequency noise. Asynchronous autozeroing is then implemented and executed at a fixed (low) frequency to remove offset and low-frequency noise. I_{ON} is then integrated into C_{ON} to generate the corresponded T_{ON} signal. Notice that, differently from the circuit in Fig. 2a, the active circuits are used to generate a current I_{ON} proportional to the voltage V_{IN} , while the capacitor C_{ON} gets reset to the voltage supply V_{DD} by means of a simple switch.

Fig. 2a Feedforward path current sensor topology

Fig. 2b Proposed peak current control topology

II. BOOST CONVERTER TOPOLOGY

The architecture of the proposed DC-DC-boost converter is shown in Fig. 3. It is designed to be paired with conventional inductive wireless powering to initially charge (and recharge) a supercap. During the pre-charge phase, input and output of the boost converter are shorted while the load is off. When the system starts up at 1.8V, the proposed boost converter is able to regulate the output voltage even if the supercap discharges, because of intermittent wireless received power, down to 170mV. To maximize efficiency, the converter operates in discontinuous conduction mode (DCM) with the proposed peak current control block. All internal circuits are powered by the output V_{OUT} .

The whole system is triggered by the load regulation comparator, which compares V_{BGR} with V_{OUTS} (generated by attenuating V_{OUT} with the output resistive divider R_{OUT1} , R_{OUT2}). When V_{OUT} drops below 1.77V, V_{OUTS} drops below V_{TH-} , then the load regulation comparator (CMP_{OUT}) triggers charging

phase. EN_{TC}, initially low to pre-charge V_{PEAK} to V_{OUT} , goes high when M_N turns on, and the current I_{ON} (proportional to V_{IN}) discharges V_{PEAK} . When V_{PEAK} crosses an internally generated reference V_{REF95} (95% of V_{OUT}), V_{ONF} goes low and the power switch M_N turns off. Then, the active diode, implemented with an autozeroed inverter-based comparator, conducts I_L to V_{OUT} via M_P . Once I_L crosses 0A, V_{GP} goes high and M_P turns off. The digital control block triggers a new power transfer cycle. After multiple power transfer cycles, V_{OUTS} increases above V_{TH+} , CMP_{OUT} turns low, then the system goes into the discharging phase.

To avoid short circuit currents, M_P and M_N are turned on with a fixed non-overlapping time (Δt). To reduce the output voltage ripple, it is important that the load regulation comparator is fast during the charging phase (V_{OUTS} rising), but that is not needed while V_{OUT} drops. Since for μW loads, the fall-times for V_{OUT} are typically much longer than the rise times, the comparator is implemented with 2 separate ones. A high-speed, high-power one, active when V_{OUT} rises, and a 20x lower power one which takes over when V_{OUT} discharges.

Fig. 3 Proposed DC-DC boost converter system overview

Fig. 4 Detailed schematic of the peak current control block

III. PROPOSED PEAK CURRENT CONTROL BLOCK

The peak current control circuit is shown in Fig. 4. The scaled input voltage V_{INS} is generated as V_{IN}/N , with $N=3$, by means of the resistive divider R_{IN1} , R_{IN2} . This is done to ensure that V_{INS} fits the TC input dynamic range. A switch-cap level shifter provides a proper DC biasing of the TC input stage (with common mode to V_{BGR}). The 1nA super source followers impose the differential input voltage (V_{INS}) over a switched-capacitor resistor ($C_1=256fF$). Therefore, the equivalent switched-capacitor resistance (R_{eq}) can be expressed as $R_{eq}=T_R / C_1$. The current flowing through R_{eq} can be written as $I_R=V_{INS} / R_{eq}$. The TC should be autozeroed, because V_{INS} can get as low as 56 mV and thus the TC's offset and low-frequency noise needs to be suppressed to enhance the current control accuracy. The current in M_{N5} is the difference between the TC output current flowing through M_{P3} (I_{TC}) and the sampled offset current flowing through M_{N4} (I_{AZ}). The diode voltage M_{N5} is then sampled and stored in C_2 to bias M_{N7} , which generates the current I_{ON} to discharge the capacitance C_{ON} (pre-charged to V_{OUT} at the start of each cycle). Then I_{MN5} is magnified by a factor $K=10,000$ to produce the I_{ON} current.

The current I_{ON} can be expressed as $I_{ON}=K*M*I_R$. An autozeroed inverter-based comparator (shown in Fig. 3) generates the final timing signal V_{ONF} . The charging time of the inductor T_{ON} can then be expressed as:

$$T_{ON} = \frac{C_{ON} * (V_{OUT} - V_{REF})}{I_{ON}} \quad (1)$$

We can re-write the discharge time T_{ON} as the function of V_{IN} :

$$T_{ON} = \frac{C_{ON} * (V_{OUT} - V_{REF95}) * (T_R / C_1) * N}{K * M * V_{IN}} \quad (2)$$

From (2), it is clear that T_{ON} is inversely proportional to V_{IN} as required. When the coil inductance L is known, the parameters K and M are chosen such that the target value of the peak current becomes:

$$I_{PEAK} = \frac{C_{ON} * (V_{OUT} - V_{REF95}) * (T_R / C_1) * N}{K * M * L} \quad (3)$$

IV. MEASUREMENT RESULT

This chip was implemented in a 180nm CMOS process. Fig. 5 shows the chip micrograph. The active area of the chip is $1.493 \text{ mm} \times 0.850 \text{ mm}$ (1.269 mm^2).

Fig. 5 Chip minigraph of the proposed ASIC

Fig. 6a Measured operation of the converter ($V_{IN}=1.1V$) with V_{GN} and V_{OUT}

Fig. 6b Measured peak current under different V_{IN}

Fig. 6a shows a typical measurement result of the boost converter operating with $V_{IN}=1.1V$. The gate voltage (V_{GN}) of the switch M_N is shown alongside the regulated V_{OUT} for a load of $96\mu A$. When V_{OUT} drops below $1.77V$, the regulation loop kicks in as expected. Fig. 6b shows the peak current I_{PEAK} as function of V_{IN} . The result shows that the peak current stays close to its optimal value of $50mA$ in a large input voltage range ($170mV$ to $1.8V$). The peak current is maintained within a range of $[-6.75\%, +6.18\%]$ of its nominal value over a V_{IN} variation of more than $10x$.

Fig. 7a Measured power conversion efficiency

Fig. 7b Measured DC load regulation

Fig. 7a shows the PCE as a function of V_{IN} and load current. Note that a peak PCE of 95.82% was achieved at $V_{IN}=1.7V$ and $P_{out}=55.76\mu W$. Fig. 7b shows the DC load regulation of the proposed converter. The complete ASIC has a quiescent current of only $350nA$ while the V_{OUT} and V_{IN} resistive dividers (implemented off-chip for testing flexibility) consume an additional $650nA$, which could be further reduced with

integrated switch-cap dividers in a future iteration. TABLE I shows the comparison with state-of-the-art works using $\sim nH$ inductors. This chip operates at the lowest input voltage ($170mV$), with the largest min-to-max input voltage range ($10.58x$) and with the lowest quiescent current ($1\mu A$ including off-chip voltage dividers).

TABLE I COMPARISON WITH STATE-OF-THE-ART WORKS

	[1] ESSCIRC 2007	[3] TPE 2018	[4] JSSC 2021	[5] TPE 2022	This Work
Tech. (nm)	180	180	180	180	180
Inductor	18nH (bondwire)	20nH (off chip) 30nH (bondwire)	300nH	100nH	100nH
Conduction Mode	CM PWM	VM PWM	CM AOT	CM AOT	CM AOT
Max / Min V_{IN}	1.25	2.7	1.83	1.33	10.58
V_{IN} (V)	1.6-2.0	1.0-2.7	1.8-3.3	1.8-2.4	0.17-1.8
V_{OUT} (V)	2.5-4.0	3.2	3.0-4.5	3.3	1.8
Peak Efficiency	63.00%	75.90%	94.50%	91.50%	95.82%
Quiescent Current	660 μA **	258 μA	25 μA **	8mA**	1μA / 350nA
Chip Area (mm ²)	2.25	2.25	1.672	1.456	2.24

*: Includes all external resistance; **: Estimation from Figure or Datasheet

V. CONCLUSION

This work proposes a DCM DC-DC boost converter for low power miniature medical implants. To overcome the power consumption of high-speed control loops that come with small inductors, a novel peak current control block is proposed. Thanks to this ultra-low power control system, this work achieves the minimum input voltage ($170mV$), the lowest quiescent current ($1\mu A$), the highest PCE (95.82%) and the largest min-to-max input voltage range ($\times 10.58$) for $\sim nH$ inductive converters. The combination of all the above-mentioned characteristics makes this converter well suited for miniature active medical implants operating from supercapacitors.

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